

Micro Finance - Current Status and Growing Concerns in India

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Abstract

One of the highest challenges before the Indian sub-continent which accommodates more than one-third of the population is poverty. The Government of India with its concern started various poverty alleviation programs, but they have failed to deliver the objectives to the level which is desired. The reasons may be many such as failure to reach the target group, loopholes in the system, developing a robust mechanism to name a few. Many countries including India experimented with subsidized credit which only led to increasing in the NPAs. The microfinance has come forward to fill up this gap. Microfinance sector has grown rapidly over the past few eras. Today it has evolved into a vibrant industry exhibiting a variety of business models. Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) in India exist as NGOs (registered as societies or trusts), Section 25 companies and Non-Banking Financial Companies (NBFCs). Commercial Banks, Regional Rural Banks (RRBs), cooperative societies and other large lenders have played ankey role in providing refinance facility to MFIs.

Keywords: Grammen Banks, India, Microfinance, NABARD, Poverty.

Introduction

"Microfinance is the provision of financial services to low-income clients or solidarity lending groups including consumers and the self-employed, who traditionally lack access to banking and related services." Microfinance is not just about giving microcredit to the poor quite it is an economic development tool whose objective is to assist the poor to work their way out of poverty. It covers a wide range of services like credit, savings, insurance, remittance and also non-financial services like training, counseling, etc. According to the World Bank, although there are over 10,000 microfinance institutions (MFIs), serving over 150 million poor people in developing countries, they only reached 4 percent of the potential market.

In recent years, there has been tremendous growth in the number of microfinance

Borrowers, growing over the past five years, between 25 and 30 percent annually and it is expected similar development in the coming years 18 Microfinance industry is segmented, ranging from very small NGOs with few clients to large institutions with millions of clients, and it is a highly concentrated industry. One need only considers that the median share of the largest MFI in a country is one-third of the entire market and the median part of the top ten MFIs is about 95

percent of all industry¹⁹. The microfinance investment market is also growing in size and maturity, and it is increasing the need of investors for transparency through market research, data provider and analysis of MFIs.

Salient features of Microfinance

- Borrowers are from the low-income group
- Loans are of a small amount
- Short duration loans
- High frequency of repayment
- Credits are generally taken for income generation purpose

Need for Microfinance

According to the latest research done by the World Bank, India is home to almost one-third of the world's poor (surviving on an equivalent of one dollar a day). Though much central governments and state government poverty alleviation programs were currently active in India, microfinance plays a foremost contributor to financial inclusion. In the past few decades, it has helped out remarkably in eradicating poverty. Reports show that people who have taken microfinance have been able to increase their income and hence the standard of living.

About half of the Indian population still doesn't have a savings bank account, and they are poor of all banking services. Poor also need financial services to fulfill their needs like consumption, a building of assets and protection against risk. Microfinance institutions serve as a supplement to banks and in some sense a better one too. These institutions not only offer microcredit but they also provide other financial services like savings, insurance, remittance and non-financial services like individual counseling, training, and support to start own business and the most important in a convenient way. The borrower receives all these services at her/his door and in most cases with a repayment schedule of borrower's convenience. But all this comes at a cost and the interest rates charged by these institutions are higher than commercial banks and vary widely from 10 to 30 percent. Some claim that the interest rates charged by some of these institutions are very high while others feel that considering the cost of capital and the cost incurred in giving the service, the high-interest rates are justified.

Channels of Microfinance

In India microfinance operates through two channels:

1. SHG – Bank Linkage Programme (SBLP)
2. Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs)

The Growth of Microfinance in India

Microfinance in India started in the early 1980s with small efforts at forming informal self-help groups (SHG) to provide access to much-needed savings and credit services to the marginal population more importantly in rural areas.

The World Bank has called South Asia the “cradle of microfinance.” Statistics indicate that some 45% of all the people in the world who use microfinance services are living in South Asia. However, the overall percentage of the poor and vulnerable people with access to financial services remains small, amounting to less than 20 % of poor households in India.

With financial inclusion emerging as a major policy objective in the country, Microfinance has occupied center stage as a promising conduit for extending financial services to unbanked sections of population. The microfinance sector has emerged as one of the most promising tool for

ameliorating poverty in India. The microfinance in India involves forming self-help groups, usually a group of 5 to 20 persons and providing them credit through bank linkage. Therefore in India, it is often called as SHG Bank linkage programme.

With the growth of microfinance industry many small and large Microfinance Institutions (MFI) had emerged in India and the largest MFI is SKS Microfinance Ltd which is also listed in the stock market, only such institution in India.

The microfinance sector has a healthy growth rate, and it is currently a Rs.20,000 Cr. industry. The SHG-Bank Linkage Programme and the Microfinance Institutions put together achieved growth in their customer base by about 10.8 percent. The combined borrowing customer base increased to 93.9 million from 86.3million in the previous year.

Despite healthy growth over the years, their number of concerns have emerged related to the sector, like regulation, transparent pricing, low financial literacy, etc. In addition to these concerns there are a few emerging concerns like cluster formation, insufficient funds, multiple lending and over-indebtedness which are arising because of the increasing competition among the MFIs.

On a national level, there has been a spate of actions taken to strengthen the regulation of MF sector including, enactment of microfinance regulation bill by the Government of Andhra Pradesh, implementation of sector-specific regulation by Reserve Bank of India and most recently, a release of Draft Microfinance Institutions Bill. RBI credit policy capped household income at Rs.120000/- and credit limit at Rs.50000 for all MFI customers.

Challenges faced by Microfinance in India

Key challenges faced by microfinance in India are challenges related to access to finance, governance, and management, demand for low-interest rates and managing competition. It further adds that:

- The single biggest task for microfinance lies in the area of training and capacity development;
- On the supply side, there is a lack of service providers and comprehensive, integrated and relevant training modules
- Limited reach in the northern and eastern parts of the country
- A range of products tends to be limited to simple credit offerings
- On the demand side, not enough attention is being paid to training for senior management
- An absence of social audit in many cases

Supply of Microfinance Services In India

The Indian Microfinance sector is characterized by a variety of microfinance service providers. These include apex financial institutions like the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD), Small Industrial Development Bank of India (SIDBI) and government-owned schemes and societies like RashtriyaMahilaKosh (RMK), formal sector financial institutions, Commercial Banks, Regional Rural Banks (RRBs), member-based institutions like Co-operatives, Mutually Aided Co-operative Societies (MACS), SHG Federations, private sector companies, specialized Non-Banking Financial Corporations (NBFCs), Societies, Trusts, etc. For commercial banks, priority sector lending targets and worthy returns are the major incentives. While their current exposure to microfinance is too small to make a difference to their overall portfolio, or even their priority sector lending portfolio, these new banks are pursuing new and innovative approaches to microfinance - as a potential business and not merely as a social or priority sector lending obligation. Encouraged by the early results, the new private sector banks, most notably ICICI Bank, but also AXIS Bank and HDFC Bank, are actively seeking exposure in the microfinance sector. Different kinds of MFIs are also scaling up their activities with product diversification. These

MFIs are working with a strategy to upscale their service for financial inclusion on a commercial basis. International banks such as ABN-Amro, City Financial, etc. are also showing interest in microfinance in the region. These banks enter microfinance with ambitions to grow in the emerging sector and are willing to invest in medium or long-term projects. The now-popular concept of the 'Bottom of the Pyramid'- entering low-end mass markets in poor regions that may bring large corporate growth fuels such ambitions.

Delivery Models of Microfinance in India

Various traditional, as well as innovative approaches, have been adopted by formal Commercial Banks, Regional Rural Banks, and Co-operatives as well as MFIs, for increasing the credit flow to the segments mentioned above.

Group-Based Model

Within the group based category, there are two sub-categories viz. Self Help Group (SHG) and the Grameen Bank model. Of these two models, the SHG model is most commonly used by many organizations in India. In this model, high emphasis is given on savings and credit activities. The SHG-bank Linkage Programme adopted by NABARD with partner agencies has emerged as an attractive mode of credit delivery model. Apart from the SHG-bank linkage programme, many NGOs are using a variety of delivery mechanisms (including adaptations of Bangladesh Grameen Bank) for providing microcredit services with financial support from external donors and other apex institutions, including the RashtriyaMahilaKosh (RMK) set up by the Government and the SIDBI Foundation for micro-credit set up by a sister apex development institution.

Non-Banking Financial Corporation (NBFC) Model

This model has the belief that the poor are bankable and lending to them is commercially viable. This model works on banking principles with a focus on both saving and credit activities. Financial services are provided to the clients either directly or through SHGs the core element of this model is profit making with strict monetary discipline to reach the unreachable. In India, this type of delivery model is very popular in the corporate world.

Wholesale Banking Model

The Wholesale Banking Model seeks to assist many NGOs working previously on nonfinancial development issues like poverty, health, literacy, eco-restorations,etc. but that has now taken microfinance as an add-on programme. MFIs are adopting this model act as second-tier MFIs. The model has the features of promptness and unique package of providing both loans and capacity building support to its partners. The model entails making loans to financial intermediaries in the form of NGOs/MFIs/ SHG Federations rather than directly to groups or members.

Individual Banking Based Model

The Individual Banking Model is a formal banking model in which individual clients are provided financial services. The group formation costs are not incurred or are quite low. Formal financial institutions like Commercial Banks, Regional Rural Banks, and Cooperative Banks adopt predominantly individual banking based model for lending to the unorganized sector, comprising both farm and non-farm sectors. While the separate banking model is suited to lending to enterprises, the group approach is best suited to lending to pre-micro enterprises and micro-enterprises.

Co-operative Model

The Co-operative model is another model of credit delivery in which loans are given to individuals. All borrowers are members of the organization. Co-operatives are large, heterogeneous and formal organizations and different from small homogenous and informal SHGs. The organization which has vastly been successful in co-operative form in India is Saha-vikas or Co-operative Development Foundation (CDF).

Public Interventions In Microfinance Programmes In India

The government of India has initiated various programmes in the area of microfinance. The most important of the programmes using the SHG approach is the Swamajayanti Gram Swarojgar Yojana (SGSY) launched in 1999. Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA), Indira Mahila Yojana, Swa-Shakti and Swayamsidha, Rastriya Mahila Kosh (RMK) are other examples of government initiatives to enhance the living conditions of the poor especially women through self-employment activities.

Indira Mahila Yojana (IMY)

Indira Mahila Yojana (IMY) was the first Self Help Group-based women's empowerment programme, launched by Ministry of Women and Child Development in 1995-96 in 238 blocks in the country. The task entrusted to the IMY was to create a sense of awareness, particularly among the rural women, to enable them to become active participants in the process of social transformation and regeneration. The main objectives of the scheme were to address the capacity building, income and awareness generation-related requirements of the women, and it proposed to converge of all the available schemes for the advancement of women. IMY was a centrally sponsored scheme implemented through the state government aimed at converging of all the social development programmes to meet women's needs and integrate various sectoral allocations at the district level for addressing their needs. As a part of this strategy, the Self Help Groups which were formed at the grassroots level would have been able to give women access to the various programmes implemented by various departments. The major thrust of IMY was the formation of Self-Help Groups at the village or the Anganwadi level, to establish a strong base for women at the Panchayat level to prioritize women's needs.

Swa-Shakti Project

Swa-Shakti, a project jointly assisted by the World Bank, International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) and Government of India, was started by the Women's Development Corporations of seven States¹⁰. The project strategy involved organizing women into SHGs that work towards gaining access to and control over physical, social and economic resources as well as political processes. The project mainly focused on various aspects of capacity-building of the SHGs and the implementing agencies; access to credit and inputs for starting feasible on-farm and off-farm income generating activities; access to information on health, nutrition, natural resource management, improved agricultural practices and animal husbandry and awareness generation regarding legal rights, laws and delivery of services. Swa-Shakti aimed at the empowerment of women by facilitating a process of social change.

Swayam Siddha Project

An improved version of the Self Help Group based women's empowerment programme, namely Swayamsiddha, was launched in February 2001 in 650 blocks, including the 238 IMY blocks in 35 States/UTs, with a total budget of Rs. 116.30 crores. The scheme was ended on 31st March 2008

but the SHGs are still working. Swayamsiddha is an integrated project for the development and empowerment of women. The scheme was implemented through the ICDS set up in most of the States. It was based on the formation of women into SHGs with emphasis on converging services, developing access to micro-credit and promoting micro-enterprises. The long-term objective of the scheme was to achieve an all-round empowerment of women, especially socially and economically, by ensuring their direct access to, and control over, resources through a sustained process of mobilization and convergence of all ongoing sectorial programmes.

Development of Women and Children in Rural Area (DWCRA)

Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA) was launched in the Integrated Rural Development Programme (IRDP) for providing self-employment opportunities to poor women on a group basis in the Seventh Plan. It aimed to empower rural women living Below Poverty Line by way of organizing them to create sustainable income-generating activities through self-employment. A unique feature of DWCRA, unlike other IRDP components, was that along with the improvement in income, it also focused on access to health, education, safe drinking water, sanitation, and nutrition. Another unique feature of this programme was that it emphasized on group approach to undertake economic activity and simultaneously to get other benefits collectively.

Integrated Rural Development Programme (IRDP)

In 1977, the Integrated Rural Development Programme (IRDP) was launched as a comprehensive programme covering all sectors of the rural economy. The overall goal of the program was to enhance the income of the rural poor sufficiently so as to enable them to cross the poverty line. The Programme used the banking channel to direct assistance (by way of a combination of credit and subsidy) to households below the official poverty line. Thus the target group of the programme was the small and marginal farmers, landless agricultural laborers, rural artisans, socially and economically deprived sections like SC/ST, women and the physically handicapped.

SwarnJayanti Gram SwarozgarYojana (SGSY)

Most of the poverty alleviation programmes could not reduce the incidence of poverty substantially for a variety of reasons. Wrong selection of beneficiaries, leakage, corruption, and malpractices, an absence of backward and forward linkage in the projects and inadequacy in delivery and monitoring of credit were the few factors identified by the Agricultural Credit Review Committee (1988). According to Narasimhan committee (1998), 'one-shot' operation in lending and failure to develop sustainable bank-client relationship was another deficiency. Unviable projects and non-utilization of local resources/expertise led to rising in debtless of IRDP beneficiaries, while DWCRA could not by and large establish viable groups and the training facility under TRYSEM was ineffective to exercise salutary impact on functional skills of the beneficiaries. It was felt that the fragmented approaches with a multiplication of the schemes were not able to focus on the needs of the rural poor in a coherently.

Conclusion

Credit is one of the many infrastructural needs of a micro-entrepreneur. Infrastructural needs may be less important for some non-agricultural rural entrepreneurial activities such as cycle repairing, tailoring, etc. but they are very important for agriculture which being one of the most significant rural micro-enterprises in developing economies. They often have to act on trust and cannot easily engage with the State and formal private sector who normally work with written documents.

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